

Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines

SO2-D2.1.4 Priority List of COVID-19 Adverse events of special interest

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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

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Description of the deliverable	This deliverable provides the fifth update to the Priority List of potential Adverse events of special interest relevant to COVID-19 vaccine trials. Past updates focused on COVID-19 disease course and complications whereas this one shifts the emphasis to what has been observed for COVID-19 vaccines currently in use. It is limited to countries with pharmacovigilance programs in place that are able to monitor large populations (United States, Canada, Australia, United Kingdom, European Union).
Key words	Toolbox, adverse events of special interest, guidance documents, Long COVID

DOCUMENT HISTORY

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AEFI	Adverse event following immunization
AESI	Adverse event of special interest
CDC	Center for Disease Control and Prevention
CEPI	Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness and Innovation
CLS	Capillary Leak Syndrome
DIC	Disseminated intravascular coagulation
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EU	European Union
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GACVS	Global Advisory Committee on Vaccine Safety
GBS	Guillain Barre Syndrome
HC	Health Canada
ITP	Immune Thrombocytopenia
MHRA	Medicines & Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
MIS-A	Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in adults
MIS-C	Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children
PHAC	Public Health Agency of Canada
PRAC	Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee
SOCV	Single organ cutaneous vasculitis
SPEAC	Safety Platform for Emergency vACCines
TGA	Therapeutic Goods Administration
TTS	Thrombocytopenia and Thrombosis Syndrome
UK	United Kingdom
UMC	Uppsala Monitoring Center
USA	United States of America
VAERS	Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System
WHO	World Health Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As part of its work to harmonize safety assessment of CEPI-funded vaccines, the Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines (SPEAC) Project has generated a list of adverse events of special interest (AESI) for safety monitoring based on one or more of the following criteria:

- 1) known association with immunization or a specific vaccine platform;
- 2) occurrence during wild-type disease as a result of viral replication and/or immunopathogenesis.
- 3) theoretical association based on animal models;

COVID-19 is relatively unique as an emerging pandemic pathogen with an ever-expanding variety of clinical manifestations which might occur as presenting complaints and/or emerge during and following the course of acute disease. The first SPEAC COVID-19 AESI list was created in March 2020 based on the experience in China. As the global experience with the SARS-CoV-2 viral infection expanded, a first update to the list was done in May 2020 and subsequently adopted by the WHO Global Advisory Committee on Vaccine Safety (GACVS) at their May 27-28, 2020, meeting. Subsequently, SPEAC implemented a systematic review process to ensure an ongoing understanding of the full spectrum of COVID-19 disease and modification of the AESI list accordingly. The second update was completed in September 2020 with no AESIs added to the May 2020 list. The third update was completed in December 2020 and three new entities were added to the AESI list: rhabdomyolysis, subacute thyroiditis, and acute pancreatitis.

This document provides methods and results of the fifth update to the COVID-19 AESI list, completed in October 2022. The primary objective was to look for possible new entities to add to the COVID-19 AESI list by focusing on safety signals identified during COVID-19 mass immunization campaigns conducted in regions with strength in pharmacovigilance and signal assessment including European countries participating in the Eudravigilance system, the United Kingdom (Yellow Card Scheme), Australia, Canada and the United States of America. Safety issues identified by WHO programs including the Uppsala Monitoring Program (VIGIBASE) and the Global Advisory Committee for Vaccine Safety were also included. The search was internet based, using the official websites of each of the country / region programs.

Based on the findings presented in this update SPEAC recommends the COVID-19 AESI list be updated to include the following:

- Thrombocytopenia and Thrombosis Syndrome
- Immune thrombocytopenia (ITP) – while thrombocytopenia is on the list, the existing Brighton case definition focuses only on thrombocytopenia, and thus putting ITP on the list would draw attention to the need for an updated case definition.
- Capillary Leak Syndrome
- Facial swelling in individuals with dermal fillers
- Dizziness and tinnitus
- Extensive limb swelling (currently only identified following Comirnaty within UK's Yellow Card Scheme)
- Delayed. Hypersensitivity reaction
- Syncope

1. Background

CEPI has contracted with the Brighton Collaboration, through the Task Force for Global Health, to harmonize the safety assessment of CEPI-funded vaccines via its Safety Platform for Emergency vACCines (SPEAC) Project.

A key aspect of this harmonization has been creation of lists of priority potential adverse events of special interest (AESI) that are relevant to vaccines targeting CEPI target diseases. Given the emerging and pandemic nature of COVID-19, ongoing systematic reviews of the literature have been necessary and there have been several updates to the AESI list. These are summarized in the table below along with links to each of the landscape updates done for COVID-19.

TABLE 1. Evolution of COVID-19 AESI literature reviews and AESI list and updates.

COVID-19 AESI List	Deliverable Document (with link)	Date Completed	Literature Review End Date	Comment
Initial list	SO1-D2.3 V1.1	Mar 5, 2020	February 2020	Based on first 5 publications from China
1 st Update	SO1-D2.3 V1.2	May 25, 2020	May 16, 2020	Adopted by WHO GACVS ¹
2 nd Update	SO2-D2.1.1	Sept 9, 2020	August 8, 2020	No new AESI added
3 rd Update	SO2-D2.1.2	Jan 11, 2021	November 13, 2020	Three AESI added: acute pancreatitis, rhabdomyolysis, and subacute thyroiditis
4 th Update	SO2-D2.1.3 Part 1 SO2-D2.1.3 Part 2	Sept, 2021	July 12, 2021 August 2, 2021	No AESI added, but Brighton Case definition to be done for Long COVID.

For the 5th update to the list, a shift in focus from COVID-19 disease to experience with safety issues observed following authorization of COVID-19 vaccines has been made.

2. Objectives

The overall objective is to identify new adverse events that are potentially associated with COVID-19 vaccines that have not already been placed on the COVID-19 AESI list. Specifically:

1. To review COVID-19 vaccine safety signals that have been assessed by regulatory authorities in the European Union, United Kingdom, United States and Australia.
2. To review online summaries of COVID-19 vaccine safety data from pharmacovigilance systems in the United States, Canada, WHO-UMC and GACVS.

3. Methods

3.1 Online search of key Regulatory and Pharmacovigilance websites for vaccine safety issues associated with COVID-19 vaccines

3.1.1 European Medicines Agency (EMA) Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee (PRAC)

In the European Union pharmacovigilance is coordinated by the EMA. Eudravigilance was created and is maintained by the EMA. It is a single repository for reports of suspected adverse reactions to vaccines as well as other products. Safety signals detected via Eudravigilance are evaluated by the PRAC which publishes an online meeting summary report on a monthly basis (<https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/committees/prac/prac-agendas-minutes-highlights>; last accessed Oct 26, 2022). All meeting summary reports from May 11-14, 2020, through September 26-29, 2022, were reviewed and a summary made for all issues involving COVID-19 vaccines. In addition to making notes on the issues, any information regarding the vaccines in use and doses distributed at the time of the signal analysis was captured.

3.1.2 Australia - Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA)

The website for the TGA, which is within the Department of Health and Aged Care of the Australian Government was searched for the most recent COVID-19 vaccine safety report (<https://www.ta.gov.au/news/covid-19-vaccine-safety-reports/covid-19-vaccine-safety-report-20-10-2022>; last accessed Oct 26, 2022). The report was read in entirety and notes made regarding any safety issues that were identified and assessed. Note was also made of the vaccines in use in Australia, and doses distributed relevant to the time of the data analysis, if available.

3.1.3 Medicines & Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) United Kingdom (UK).

In the UK, the MHRA runs the Yellow Card scheme to collect and monitor information on suspected safety concerns involving healthcare products. Reporting is voluntary and can be done by the public and healthcare professionals. The GOV.UK website was searched for summary analyses of Yellow Card reporting regarding COVID-19 vaccines. (found via Google search for 'MHRA yellow card summary report on COVID-19 vaccines'. Specific link [<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/coronavirus-covid-19-vaccine-adverse=reactions/coronavirus-vaccine-summary-of-yellow-card-reporting>] did not work when put into url. Alternately go to main site, <https://www.Gov.UK> site and search from there). In addition to noting issues of concern, information on vaccine types used in the UK and total vaccine doses distributed relevant to the latest safety update were captured.

3.1.4 Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), United States of America (USA)

COVID-19 vaccine safety sites at both the FDA (<https://www.fda.gov/emergency-preparedness-and-response/coronavirus-disease-2019-covid-19/covid-19-vaccines>; last accessed Oct 26, 2022) and CDC (<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/vaccines/safety/safety-of-vaccines.html>); last accessed Oct 26, 2022) were searched for summary reports of COVID-19 vaccine safety based on both active and passive surveillance programs. Data on the COVID-19 vaccines used in the USA were also searched along with the total doses distributed relevant to the most recent analyses. At the FDA site fact sheets for each of the authorized vaccines which make up the vast majority of vaccines administered in the USA were reviewed to see what if any safety concerns were included in the product information. Vaccine safety publications, listed at the CDC website were also reviewed to see if any reported on new signals.

3.1.5 World Health Organization (WHO) Websites

The Global Advisory Committee on Vaccine Safety (GACVS) holds bi-annual meetings where vaccine safety issues are discussed. The Weekly Epidemiologic Record publishes reports for each GACVS meeting (<https://www.who.int/groups/global-advisory-committee-on-vaccine-safety/committee-reports>; last accessed Oct 26, 2022). All reports for meetings held since the start of COVID-19 vaccination were reviewed for safety issues: Jun 2021, Sept 2021, Dec 2021 and June 2022).

The Uppsala Monitoring Center (UMC) collects AEFI reports from global sources and conducts analyses of reporting disproportionality to identify possible signals. The UMC website was searched for any published signal assessment related to COVID-19 vaccines (<https://who-umc.org/signal-work/signal-library/>; last accessed October 26, 2022). At the signal library site, the embedded search function was used to look for any publications on new vaccine safety signals. Reports on already recognized signals, such as myocarditis or TTS were not retrieved.

3.1.6 Health Canada (HC) and the Public Health Agency of Canada (PHAC)

HC and PHAC jointly oversee Canada's vaccine pharmacovigilance system. Canada's 10 provinces and 3 territories administered COVID-19 vaccines during the pandemic and were the source of the vast majority of AEFI reports. In addition, HC's Canada Vigilance system collects reports primarily from Market Authorization Holders (MAH) for all vaccines distributed in Canada. There is also a national pediatric hospital based active surveillance system called IMPACT (Immunization Monitoring Program, ACTIVE) which submits AEFI reports to PHAC for listed AESIs if a child is hospitalized and it is determined that there was a recent vaccination. Regular summary reports are published on the HC website (www.health-infobaase.canada.ca/covid-19/vaccine-safety/; last accessed Oct 26, 2022). The most recent report was downloaded and reviewed for any newly identified AE signals.

3.1.7 Google Search for Global Vaccine Use

To supplement what was learned about vaccines used in country and estimated doses administered, a general Google search (<all global COVID-19 vaccines>) was done to try to determine the global use of COVID-19 vaccines. This was needed to determine the extent to which searching on the websites noted above would likely miss pharmacovigilance data on some COVID-19 vaccines.

3.1.8 Rationale for Adding Items to AESI List

The following rationales were used as the basis for adding an AESI to the COVID-19 list (if not already on the list):

- Signal assessed by one or more Regulatory bodies and validated
- Regulatory requirement of vaccine manufacturer to add an adverse event to the official product information document.

4. Results

4.1 COVID-19 Vaccine Safety Issues Identified on Regulatory and Pharmacovigilance Websites

4.1.1 PRAC

The main vaccines in use in the EU during this time frame were Comirnaty (Pfizer), Spikevax (Moderna), Vaxzevria (Oxford/AstraZeneca), Ad26.CoV.2S (Janssen). Several safety signals were identified and reviewed by PRAC. These are summarized in Table 1 in terms of implicated vaccine(s), when first discussed and review conclusion, if any, and action taken, if any. There were four identified safety signals for events not included in the COVID-19 AESI list: Capillary leak syndrome; Dizziness and tinnitus; Localized swelling at sites containing dermal fillers; Thrombocytopenia and Thrombosis syndrome (TTS).

TABLE 1. PRAC signals reviewed. The red font identifies confirmed signals for AESI that were not on the SPEAC COVID-19 AESI list

AE Signal	Vaccine(s)	Date first discussed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PRAC conclusion Recommended action
Anaphylaxis	Vaxzevria	Mar 8-11/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possible link Update product info
Autoimmune hepatitis	Comirnaty Spikevax	Apr 4-7/22	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No validated signal No change to product info
Capillary leak syndrome	Vaxzevria	Apr 6-9/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Still under review; no conclusions yet
	Ad26.CO2.S	Jun 7-10/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contraindicate further doses for those who have had CLS Update product info
	Spikevax	Oct 25-28/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deemed a safety signal for flare-ups but not for new onset cases Add a warning re potential for flare-up in those with past history of CLS
Dizziness and tinnitus	Ad26.CO2.S	Aug 5/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possible link to vaccination Update product info
GBS	Vaxzevria	May 3-6/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update product info
ITP	Comirnaty Spikevax	March/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Starting review of possible signal
	Ad26.CO2.S	Aug 5/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update product info
	Vaxzevria	Sep27-30/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update product info
Localized swelling at dermal filler sites	Comirnaty	Mar8-11/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reasonable possibility of causal association among those with dermal fillers Update product info
Menstrual disorders	COVID-19 vaccines	Aug 5/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common events; no evidence yet for causal link
Menstrual - heavy bleeding	Comirnaty Spikevax	Feb 7-10/22	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None Ask MAHs for updated cumulative review
Menstrual - amenorrhea	Comirnaty Spikevax	Feb 7-10/22	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient data for causality Continue to review

MIS	Comirnaty	Aug30-Sep2/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 cases reported, insufficient evidence to consider a link No need to update product info
Myocarditis	Comirnaty Moderna	May 3-6/21 Nov29-Dec2/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List as new side effect for both vaccines Risk $\leq 1/10,000$
Small vessel vasculitis	Ad26.COVS.2.S	Mar 7-10/22	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 21 global cases; 10 consistent with SOCV; update product info as a side effect Continue to monitor
Thromboembolic events	Vaxzevria	Mar 8-11/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No further mention other than as part of TTS
	Ad26.COVS.2.S	Apr 6-9/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update product info listing as a rare side effect
Thrombocytopenia	Vaxzevria Comirnaty Spikevax	Mar 8-11/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No further mention of this in the PRAC meeting reports, other than in association with TTS
Thrombocytopenia with Thrombosis	Vaxzevria	Apr 6-9/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update product info; list as a rare side effect
	Ad26.COVS.2.S	May 3-6/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update product info, but risk-benefit still favours vaccination
	Comirnaty Spikevax	May 3-6/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No safety signal declared
Transverse myelitis	Vaxzevria Ad26.COVS.2.S	Jan 10-13/21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update produce info for both vaccines Continue to monitor

4.1.2 TGA

The main vaccines in use in Australia were Comirnaty (Pfizer), Spikevax (Moderna), Vaxzevria (Oxford/AstraZeneca), and Nuvaxovid (Novavax). The most recent update on vaccine safety at the TGA site was dated October 16, 2022. Identified issues which continue to be carefully monitored include:

- Myocarditis and pericarditis after Comirnaty (reporting rate of 1-2 cases/100,000 immunized) and Spikevax (reporting rate of 2/100,000 immunized)
 - Cases were more common after the 2nd dose in 12–17-year-old boys (13/100,000 receiving Comirnaty and 24/100,000 receiving Spikevax) and men <30 years old (9/100,000 Comirnaty and 23/100,000 Spikevax)
- TTS after Vaxzevria in adults (reporting rate of 2.1 / 100,000 first doses and 0.3/100,000 2nd doses)
- GBS after Vaxzevria in adults
- ITP after Vaxzevria in adults

The report also summarized data from 48,532 AEFI reports following Vaxzevria. Based on reporting data the vaccine product info was updated to include SOCV and capillary leak syndrome, but both were noted to occur very rarely. Similarly, very rare reports of transverse myelitis, ADEM and VTE without thrombocytopenia were noted but no reporting rates given. Tinnitus was reported uncommonly.

Only 935 AEFI reports following Nuvaxovid were received but these included 9 reports of myocarditis and 30 of pericarditis. The report also noted cases of anaphylaxis, paraesthesia and hypoaesthesia.

4.1.3 UK Yellow Card Scheme

The main vaccines in use in the United Kingdom during this time frame were Comirnaty (Pfizer), Spikevax (Moderna), Vaxzevria (Oxford/AstraZeneca) and Nuvaxovid (Novavax). Table 2 summarizes doses administered for each up to September 28, 2022.

TABLE 2. UK COVID-19 Vaccine Campaign doses administered to Sept 28, 2022

Vaccine	1 st doses	2 nd doses	3 rd /booster doses	Yellow cards	Suspected reactions
Comirnaty	27.2 million	25.0 million	30.9 million	173,381	499,965
Vaxzevria	24.9 million	24.2 million	59,000	246,393	873,051
Spikevax	9.4 million (not broken down by dose)			42,436	138,950
Novavax	Not provided but only recently approved as a booster dose for those who can't receive mRNA vaccine			14	28

The report summarized several safety issues for which detailed assessments have been undertaken, including:

- Anaphylaxis
- Bell's palsy: concluded may be increased risk following COVID-19 vaccines including both mRNA vaccines and Vaxzevria (product info updated for all)
- Transverse myelitis: 128 reports post Vaxzevria (< 1/100,000 doses but concluded that there may be an association), 41 after Comirnaty and 7 after Spikevax
- TTS: observed incidence of 15.9 cases/million doses of Vaxzevria; 2nd doses contraindicated if an episode follows the first dose. Total of 32 reports following Comirnaty and 8 following Spikevax.
- Thromboembolic events without thrombocytopenia: possible link with Vaxzevria; continuing to monitor closely
- ITP: possible link with Vaxzevria – reporting rate of 5 cases/million doses; notably a history of prior ITP episodes or underlying condition known to be associated with ITP in 10-20% of cases. Product info updated.
- Capillary leak syndrome (CLS)
 - 18 reports following Vaxzevria of which 3 had a prior history of CLS
 - No association found between Spikevax and new onset CLS but noted a potential risk for flare-up if history of prior episode
 - Comirnaty – no suggestion of association with either new onset or flare-up of CLS
- Menstrual disorders: 51,500 reports following 75.2 million COVID-19 vaccine doses (not identified by brand) but most transient in nature; no causality conclusion made to date and continue to review new reports
- Myocarditis and pericarditis: report provided reporting rates / million 1st, 2nd and 3rd booster doses of Comirnaty by age group. Data not provided here as this is a well-established association and myocarditis and pericarditis were on the AESI list.
- Delayed hypersensitivity reactions
 - Predominantly seen with Spikevax (product info updated); onset 4-11 days after vaccination with rash, swelling and tenderness that could involve entire upper arm; skin itchy, painful, or warm to touch. Reaction usually self-limiting lasting no more than 1-2 days.
- GBS
 - Have had multiple reports of GBS or Miller Fisher as follows:
 - Vaxzevria: 509 GBS, 29 Miller Fisher (Product info updated)
 - Comirnaty: 111 GBS, 6 Millier Fisher

- Spikevax: 25 GBS
- Extensive swelling of the vaccinated limb
 - Rare reports following Comirnaty leading to product info update
- Facial swelling in those having received facial dermal fillers
 - Seen primarily after Spikevax and less often after Comirnaty. Product info for both vaccines updated.

Yellow card scheme data were also provided for vaccinated pregnant women. To end of May, 2022 135,000 women given 1 or more doses of COVID-19 vaccine during pregnancy have given birth; the comparable population in Scotland, to end of July 2022 is 47,000. Reported reactions were noted to be similar to those seen in non-pregnant women. Frequency of miscarriage or stillbirth was lower than the background rates of 20-25 per 1000 pregnancies. There had been a few reports of commonly occurring congenital anomalies or obstetrical events, but no pattern for concern.

There were 4000 yellow cards submitted by women who were breastfeeding when vaccinated. The reporting reaction profile was the same as in the general population and there were no noted effects on milk supply or in the children who were breastfeeding.

Summary data were also provided for children <18 years of age with the only issue identified being reports of myocarditis or pericarditis following mRNA vaccine.

Overall, nothing new in terms of signals was seen in the U.K. relative to the PRAC assessments. The only possible exception could be extensive limb swelling, noted to be reported, rarely, after Comirnaty administration. An update to the product information was required.

4.1.4 USA FDA and CDC

The main vaccines in use in the USA during this time frame were Comirnaty (Pfizer), Spikevax (Moderna), Ad26. COV2.S (Johnson & Johnson/Janssen) and Nuvavax (Novavax). Table 3 summarizes doses administered for each up to October 19, 2022.

TABLE 3. USA COVID-19 Vaccine Campaign doses administered to Oct 19, 2022

Vaccine	1 st / 2 nd doses	booster doses
Comirnaty	375,644,351	12,382,450
Spikevax	237,609,069	6,967,658
Johnson & Johnson /Janssen	18,922,385	
Novavax	38,250	

There were extensive active and passive vaccine safety monitoring systems in place in the USA at the start of the Pandemic. Two new systems were added: a smartphone based, after-vaccination health checker called CDC v-safe; and a V-safe COVID-19 vaccine pregnancy registry.

The CDC COVID-19 vaccine safety site provided an updated safety report through Oct 24, 2022, at which point over 632 million vaccine doses had been administered (breakdown by vaccine type shown in Table 3). A total of four serious adverse event signals were noted to have been identified to date, all included in the PRAC review above: Anaphylaxis, TTS, Myocarditis / pericarditis and GBS.

Data to May 2, 2022 on pregnancy and infant outcomes were provided as part of an ACIP meeting slideset (accessible at <https://www.cdc.gov/vaccines/acip/meetings/downloads/slides-2021-09-22/09-COVID-Olson-508.pdf>). No signals of concern have been identified to date. As of May 2, 2022, a total of 23,779 pregnant women were enrolled. Notable data summaries include:

- Spontaneous abortion: 2456 women received 1 or more mRNA doses before pregnancy. Prior to 20 weeks gestation; the cumulative age-standardized risk was 12.8% (95% confidence interval of 10.8-14.8%) which was below the expected background rate.
- Infant outcomes to May 15, 2021: total of 1634 liveborns from 1613 pregnancies:
 - Preterm – 6.5% (background rate of 8-15%)
 - Small for gestational age – 2.8% (background rate of 3.5%)
 - NICU admission – 9.7% (background rate of 9.3%)
 - Neonatal / infant deaths – 0 (background rate of <1)
- Birth defects among 1574 immunized in 2nd or 3rd trimester – nothing unusual found

No recent summary safety reports were found at the FDA website. The latest published vaccine fact sheets were reviewed and noted:

- Comirnaty – August 2022 – warnings for anaphylaxis; myocarditis and pericarditis; syncope
- Spikevax – August 2022 – warnings same as those listed for Comirnaty
- Janssen – May 2022 – warnings for anaphylaxis, TTS, ITP, GBS and syncope
- Novavax – Oct 19, 2022 – warnings for anaphylaxis, myocarditis, pericarditis, syncope

Finally, there was a report near real time safety surveillance conducted using claims data from the Medicare and Medicaid services. In July 2021 4 potential adverse event signals were detected in individuals aged ≥65 years receiving Comirnaty including: pulmonary embolism, acute myocardial infarction, ITP and DIC.

4.1.5 WHO, GACVS and UMC

Since adopting the SPEAC COVID-19 AESI list in May of 2020 and since COVID-19 vaccination programs began, there have been 4 meetings of GACVS (June, Sept, and Dec 2021; June 2022). In June 2021, it was noted that a GACVS COVID-19 vaccine safety data subcommittee had been formed in December 2020, had held 12 meetings prior to the June 2021 full GACVS committee meeting and issued 7 statements related to vaccine safety issues associated with Vaxzevria and Covishield (TTS), mRNA vaccines (myocarditis) and Johnson&Johnson/Janssen vaccine (nothing specified). The report for Sept 2021 noted that the subcommittee had had 7 meetings since June and focused on myocarditis and pericarditis following mRNA vaccines and GBS associated with adenovirus vector vaccines. It was noted that they had reviewed safety signal data for Sinopharm and Covaxin vaccines, but no specific data were provided. Nothing new was reported for the Dec 2021 meeting. At the June 2022 meeting 3 emerging signals were reviewed: transverse myelitis; hearing loss and tinnitus; acute hepatitis. No details were provided. Of note relevant to acute hepatitis, PRAC reviewed autoimmune hepatitis 2 months before the GACVS meeting and concluded there was no evidence for a signal. Nothing else of note was observed although several ongoing safety reviews were mentioned including long-term impact of myocarditis, pregnancy outcomes and safety of booster doses.

A number of signals have been identified using VIGIBASE reports including:

- Appendicitis: to May 27, 2021, with an estimated 1.82 billion doses of COVID-19 vaccines administered there were 358 reports of appendicitis among a total of 900,695 ICSRs (individual case safety reports). The majority came from North America (73%), then Europe (25%) and only a few from Oceania (1.2%) and South America (0.9%). Significant disproportionality in reporting of appendicitis related terms

(appendicitis, complicated appendicitis, appendectomy) was noted for COVID-19 vaccines as a whole and for Comirnaty, Spikevax and Janssen. Of interest was fact that 31% of reports involved 45 – 64-year-olds which is outside the peak age group for appendicitis.

- Acute inflammatory neuropathies (including neuralgic amyotrophy, Bell’s palsy/other facial paralysis, GBS). Of the three conditions, disproportionality was observed only for Bell’s palsy/facial palsy for COVID-19 vaccines versus other viral vaccines.
- Neurologic adverse events: this signal assessment, done for reports to Jan 24, 2021, noted disproportionality for over 51 neurologic adverse events. No specific conclusion was made, and it was not possible to examine specific signals.

4.1.6 Canada HC and PHAC

The vaccines used in Canada include Comirnaty (Pfizer), Spikevax (Moderna), Vaxzevria (Astra Zeneca), JCOVDEN (Janssen) and Nuvaxovid (Novavax). Overall, to Sept 16, 2022, a total of 89,343,181 COVID-19 vaccine doses have been administered. For the same period there have been a total of 51,035 AEFI reports (57.1/100,000 doses) and 10,323 SAEs (11.6 / 100,000 doses). Only 2 safety signals have been identified to date: TTS and myocarditis/pericarditis.

4.1.7 Global Vaccine Usage

Table 3 summarizes COVID-19 vaccines that currently have either full or emergency use authorization by vaccine platform and tradename. The geographic distribution of countries using the vaccine(s) is shown in the last column. Excluded from the list were countries using vaccines for a travel indication only. Yellow highlight identifies the 9 vaccines which are currently COVAX eligible. This was derived from Wikipedia and may be subject to error.

The most pharmacovigilance data have been collected for the mRNA platform vaccines Comirnaty (Pfizer) and Spikevax (Moderna); Adenovirus vector vaccine platforms Vaxzevria (ChAdOx-1, Oxford/Astra Zeneca) and Ad26.COV2.S (Janssen, Johnson & Johnson); and a protein subunit vaccine, NVX COVI2373 (Novavax). The COVAX eligible vaccines with extensive use but less certain pharmacovigilance includes inactivated SARS-CoV-2 vaccines CoronaVac (Sinovac) and BBIBP Cor-V (Sinopharm) both of which are being used primarily in China as well as the Middle East, Africa, Central and South America. Another inactivated vaccine, BBV152 COVAXIN (Bharat Biotech), is being used in India, Central America and only a few South American or African countries. The Ad26 vectored Sputnik vaccine has extensive use in Russia and possibly other LMICs. It is not a COVAX eligible vaccine.

TABLE 4. COVID-19 Vaccines in Use (Yellow highlight are COVAX eligible)
(Source https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_COVID-19_vaccine_authorizations)

Platform	Vaccine tradename	Manufacturer	Full or Emergency Authorization
mRNA	Comirnaty	Pfizer/BioNTech + Fosun Pharma	Americas, Europe, Australia, New Zealand, Africa, India,
	Spikevax	Moderna/NIAID	Americas, Europe, Australia, New Zealand, Africa, India,
Adenovirus vectors	Vaxzevria (ChAdOx1-S)	Oxford/AstraZeneca	Americas, Europe, Australia, New Zealand, Africa, India,
	Ad26.COV2.S	Janssen/Johnson&Johnson	Americas, Europe, Australia (not used), New Zealand, Africa, India,

	Convidecia (Ad5)	CanSino Biological/Beijing Institute of Biotechnology	China, Argentina, Chile, Ecuador, Mexico; Hungary, Moldova; Pakistan; Indonesia, Malaysia
	Sputnik (Ad26)	Gamaleya Research Inst	Russia, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Central+South America, India, some African countries
Virus-like particle	CoVLP (Covifenz)	Medicago	Canada
Protein subunit	NVX-CoV2373	Novavax	Canada, Australia, USA, India, Europe
	Abdala	Cuba Ctr Genetic Engineering + Biotechnology	Cuba, Mexico, Nicaragua, Venezuela, St Vincent + Grenadines, Vietnam
	Zifivax	Anhui Zhifei Longcom Biopharma	China, Indonesia, Pakistan, Uzbekistan, Columbia
	MVC-COV1901	Medigen Vaccine Biologics + Dynavax	Taiwan, Paraguay
	Corbevax	Texas Children's Hospital + BioE (India)	India, Botswana
	COVAX-19 (SpikoGen)	Vaxine (Australia) + CinnaGen (Iran)	Iran
	Razi Cov Pars	Razi Vaccine + Serum Research Institute	Iran
	NVSI	National Vaccine + Serum Institute (Sinopharm)	UAR
	Noora	Baqiyatallah Univ. of Medical Sciences	Iran
	SKYCovione	SK Bioscience	South Korea
Peptide	EpiVacCorona	Russian State Research Center of Virology and Biotech	Tussia, Belarus, Turkmenistan, Cambodia, Venezuela
Conjugate vaccine	Soberana O2	Finlay Institute, Cuba	Cuba, Nicaragua, Venezuela, Iran
	Soberana Plus		Cuba, Belarus
Inactivated SARS-CoV-2	CoronaVac	Sinovac	China, Middle East, Africa, Central + South America
	BBIBP-CorV	China National Biotech Group (CNBG) Sinopharm	China, Africa, Middle East, Central & South America
	Sinopharm WIBP		China; Peru, Venezuela; UAR; Philippines; N Macedonia
	BBV152 COVAXIN	Bharat Biotech + Indian Council of Medical Research – National Institute of Virology	India, Central America, few SA + African countries
	VLA2001	Valneva SE + Dynavax	Europe
	CoviVac	Russian Academy of Sciences	Russia, Belarus, Cambodia,
	QazCovid-in	Research Inst for Biological Safety Problems, Kazakhstan	Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan
	Minhai COVID-19	Minhai Biotech Co. + Shenzhen Kangtai Biological Products Co	China, Indonesia

	COVIran Barekat	Shifa Pharmed Industrial Co. (Iran)	Iran, Nicaragua
	CAMS COVID-19	Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences (CAMS)	China
	KAKHRAVAC(MIVAC)	Iran Ministry of Defence	Iran
	Turkovac	Health Institutes of Turkey and Erciyes University	Turkey
DNA plasmid	ZyCoV-D	Cadila Healthcare (India)	India

4.1.8. Summary of Validated Signals and Updates to Vaccine Product Information

Table 5 provides a summary of the experience and actions taken to date by Regulatory authorities in Europe, Australia, United Kingdom, USA and Canada showing which events were already on the COVID-19 AESI list, and which events are newly recognized safety issues.

TABLE 5. Recognized COVID-19 Vaccine-Associated Adverse events grouped by body system

Body System or Site	Adverse Event	Vaccine	Regulatory Authority(ies)	COVID-19 AESI List Status
Allergic or Immunologic	Anaphylaxis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaxzevria • Comirnaty, Spikevax, Novavax, Ad26.COVS.2.S 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMA • FDA 	Already on list
	Delayed hypersensitivity reaction	Spikevax	MHRA	Add to list
	Single Organ Cutaneous Vasculitis (SOCV)	Ad26.COVS.2.S	FDA	Already on list
Cardiac	Myocarditis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comirnaty, Spikevax • Novavax 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMA, TGA, MHRA, FDA, HC • FDA 	Already on list
	Pericarditis	Comirnaty, Spikevax, Novavax	FDA	Already on list
Hematologic	Immune thrombocytopenia (ITP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaxzevria • Ad26.COVS.2.S 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMA, TGA • EMA, FDA 	Add to list
	Thromboembolism	Ad26.COVS.2.S	EMA	Already on list
	Thrombocytopenia with Thrombosis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaxzevria • Ad26.COVS.2.S 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMA, TGA, MHRA, HC • EMA, FDA 	Add to list
	Capillary Leak Syndrome flare up	Ad26.COVS.2.S, Spikevax	EMA	Add to list
Neurologic	Bell's Palsy	Vaxzevria, Comirnaty, Spikevax	MHRA	Already on list
	Dizziness and Tinnitus	Ad26.COVS.2.S	EMA	Add to list
	Guillain Barre Syndrome (GBS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaxzevria • Ad26.COVS.2.S 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMA, TGA, MHRA • FDA 	Already on list

	Transverse myelitis	Vaxzevria	MHRA	Already on list
Local reactions	Localized swelling at dermal filler sites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comirnaty • Spikevax 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMA, MHRA • MHRA 	Add to list
	Extensive swelling of the vaccinated limb	Comirnaty	MHRA	Add to list
Other	Syncope	Comirnaty, Spikevax, Ad26.COVS.2.S, Novavax	FDA	Add to list

5. Recommendations & discussion

Pharmacovigilance data for two mRNA vaccines (Comirnaty, Spikevax) and two adenovirus vector vaccines (Vaxzevria and Ad26.COVS.2.S) has identified several signals which have been seen and confirmed in Europe, Australia, England, USA and Canada. At this time pharmacovigilance or epidemiological data for other COVAX vaccines as listed in Table 3 are too scant to be confident that a signal has not been missed.

Of recognized or possible signals, the following events are not yet included on the SPEAC COVID-19 AESI list:

- Thrombocytopenia and Thrombosis Syndrome
- Immune thrombocytopenia (ITP) – while thrombocytopenia is on the list, the existing Brighton case definition focuses only on thrombocytopenia, and thus putting ITP on the list would draw attention to the need for an updated case definition.
- Capillary Leak Syndrome
- Facial swelling in individuals with dermal fillers
- Dizziness and tinnitus
- Extensive limb swelling (currently only identified following Comirnaty within UK's Yellow Card Scheme)
- Delayed. Hypersensitivity reaction
- Syncope

SPEAC recommends all of the above entities to be included in the COVID-19 AESI list.

The updated COVID-19 AESI list is presented in the ANNEX and will be available online as a stand-alone list for ease of reference.

ANNEXES

Annex 1

Updated (October 2022) COVID-19 AESI including status of associated Brighton case definitions

TABLE 1. Updated (October 2022) COVID-19 AESI including status of associated Brighton case definitions

AESI	Brighton Case Definition Status
Acute respiratory distress syndrome	Published
Multisystem inflammatory syndrome (children & adults) ^{3,4}	Published
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Myocarditis / pericarditis Other forms of acute cardiac injury including arrhythmias, heart failure, coronary artery disease, myocardial infarction, stress cardiomyopathy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Published No Brighton case definition to be developed but companion guide to myocarditis/pericarditis includes background rates and ICD/MedDRA codes
Thrombosis and Thromboembolism ^{3,4}	Published
Hemorrhagic disorders including DIC	Not yet started
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anosmia³ Ageusia^{3,4} 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To be submitted to Vaccine by Oct 31, 2022 No case definition to be developed
Chilblain – like lesions	Not yet started
Erythema multiforme ^{3,4}	Not yet started
Single Organ Cutaneous Vasculitis	Published
Acute kidney injury ^{3,4}	Published lab-based criteria (see *)
Acute liver injury	Published lab-based criteria (see #)
Acute pancreatitis ^{3,4}	Not yet started
Rhabdomyolysis	Not yet started
Subacute thyroiditis ⁴	Not yet started
Anaphylaxis ^{1,2}	Published
Thrombocytopenia ^{1,2,3,4}	Published
Generalized convulsion ^{1,2}	Published
Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis ⁴	Published
Guillain Barré Syndrome ^{3,4}	Published
Acute aseptic arthritis ^{r-VSV}	Published
Aseptic meningitis ^{Live vaccines}	Published
Encephalitis / Encephalomyelitis ^{Live vaccines}	Published
Bell's Palsy ^{Intranasal EColi Heat Labile Toxin Adjuvanted Vaccine}	Published
Vaccine associated enhanced disease ^{1(Formalin inactivated measles/RSV; HIV), 2(Chimeric YF Dengue), 5 (SARS / MERS-CoVs)}	Published
Thrombocytopenia and Thrombosis Syndrome⁶	Proposed case definition posted online; Working group to be formed by end of 2022
Immune Thrombocytopenia (ITP)⁶	Thrombocytopenia published; revision needed
Capillary Leak Syndrome⁶ (Flare up in individuals with prior history of capillary leak syndrome)	Not yet started
Delayed hypersensitivity reaction⁶	Not yet started
Extensive limb swelling⁶	Not yet started

Facial swelling in individuals with dermal fillers ⁶	Not yet started
Dizziness and tinnitus ⁶	Not yet started

¹ Proven association with immunization encompassing several different vaccines

² Proven association with vaccine that could theoretically be true for novel COVID-19 vaccines

³ Theoretical concern based on wild type disease immunopathogenesis

⁴ Theoretical concern related to viral replication during wild type disease

⁵ Theoretical concern because it has been demonstrated in an animal model with ≥ 1 vaccine platform

⁶ Signal recognized and validated during COVID-19 mass campaigns or regulator(s) required update to product information

* Acute kidney injury—consensus definition of Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes expert consensus group www.kdigo.org

- Increase in serum creatinine by ≥ 0.3 mg/dl (≥ 26 $\mu\text{mol/l}$) within 48 hours; OR
- Increase in serum creatinine to ≥ 1.5 times baseline, known or presumed to have occurred within prior 7 days OR
- Urine volume ≤ 0.5 ml/ kg/ hour for 6 hours

Acute liver injury – definition as used in majority of COVID-19 publications (but no international consensus):

- > 3 -fold elevation above the upper normal limit for ALT or AST OR
- > 2 -fold elevation above the upper normal limit for total serum bilirubin or GGT or ALP

• Case Definition and resources available at:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1QgF35nYcsaFN3DZTOtV_IP0TYqQzsDMUQBAd5M9brrM/edit#gid=1666959512